

Environmental benefits of lignin based eco-friendly surfactants for flotation processes towards current practices

A. Peppas^{1#}, D. Skenderas², C. Politi³, P.M. Angelopoulos⁴

¹ Antonis Peppas, School of Mining and Metallurgical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, 15780 Athens, Greece

² Doris Skenderas, School of Mining and Metallurgical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, 15780 Athens, Greece

³ Chrysa Politi, School of Mining and Metallurgical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, 15780 Athens, Greece

⁴ Panagiotis M. Angelopoulos, School of Mining and Metallurgical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, 15780 Athens, Greece

ABSTRACT – Froth flotation is known to be one of the keys enabling technologies allowing the selective separation of values from uneconomic mineral resources. Froth flotation utilizes the differences in the wettability of minerals in a three-phase system that consists of solids, gas, and water. Xanthates are currently the most used collectors in sulphide flotation, produced mainly in China. Nevertheless, the application of toxic reagents and the high amount of freshwater intake raises severe environmental concerns. In this frame, the study investigates the environmental benefits of replacing the flotation reagent of Xanthate with Lignin nanoparticles for the treatment of 1 tonne of mined ore, subjected to flotation.

Keywords: Flotation Reagents, Flotation Technology, Life Cycle Assessment, Xanthate, Lignin

INTRODUCTION

Froth flotation is a concentration process that selectively separates minerals[1]. This process is a physicochemical separation technique that exploits the difference in the surface wettability of mineral particles[2]. The ore is ground to a sufficient size to liberate desired minerals. The hydrophobic particles of the heterogenous solid mixture are made to attach the gas bubbles, carried to the froth phase and recovered as a froth product [2]. For reaching the aimed selectivity, flotation method is dependent on the reagents. Reagents are used to regulate the conditions of the flotation and modify the surface of minerals. The xanthates salts are widely used as collectors for sulphides mineral flotation.

Xanthates have their share in rubber processing, agrochemicals, textile production, and other markets [3]. Thus, the mining sector remains a major share of the overall xanthates market [4]. The projected growth of the mining industry and the focus of mining companies on extracting ores from deep underground reserves entails the consumption of higher amounts of xanthates. Besides, xanthates are used as a catalyst in the production of polyvinyl chloride (PVC). These, will drive the xanthates market leading to its steady growth [5].

corresponding author: peppas@metal.ntua.gr

Asia Pacific (APAC) holds a prominent share of the global xanthates market for both the production and consumption of xanthates. China has the dominant stake in the APAC and the global xanthates market. China's xanthates market size is forecasted to reach US\$130.5 Million by 2027, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 8.7% over the analysis period, 2020-2027 [4].

Xanthates are considered very valuable and are used for more than a century in mineral processing of sulphides ores. Xanthates are a group of synthesized toxic organic chemicals, most commonly obtained by the reaction of alcohol, hydroxide, and carbon disulphide (CS₂) [6]. Among the different types of xanthates, ethyl, isopropyl, isobutyl, amyl, and hexyl xanthates are usually preferred in the flotation process [7].

Xanthates have been characterised as hazardous, combustible, and toxic in nature. Their use involves additional costs and restrictions associated with storage, transportation and handling, among others. Their decomposition behaviour is arising concerns in terms of safety, health, and environmental impact. Decomposition has been reported to generate toxic substances such as carbon disulphide, carbonyl sulphide (COS), hydrogen sulphides, and hydrogen peroxide. The formation of toxic CS₂ comes as a result of xanthates' exposure to heat, moisture and acid leads. CS₂ can reach high vapor concentrations at room temperature resulting in a hazardous work environment. Human health can be significantly affected from being in contact with CS₂ [8]. Except for humans, xanthates and xanthates degradation pose a potential hazard for animals, soil and aquatic organisms, enzymatic system, etc. [3].

In the frame of green transition and sustainable development, there is observed the tendency for developing new, eco-friendlier solutions of similar functional standards. A novel approach, with the potential to offer a sustainable solution is the use of organosolv lignin (OL) for producing lignin micro- and nanoparticles, with the last being a promising alternative[9]. Lignin is found in abundant amounts in nature, resulting in growing interest in utilising lignin as a raw material for production of bio-products. Lignin is obtained after treatment of forest residues and side streams of the pulp industry [9]. There are three main types of lignin, sulphonated lignin, kraft lignin, and OL[10].

OL can be used in different applications as coatings, adhesives and sealants, personal care products, etc. The global OL market is projected to grow at a CAGR of 8.5% during the period 2022-2030. This is mainly due to the increased demand in pulp and paper products that will lead to higher generation OL; the favourable policies for biobased chemical production; the technological evolution regarding OL and other factors [11, 12].

Organosolv is a pulping approach that utilises organic solvents to solubilize lignin and hemicelluloses [13]. Among the different sources of lignin, OL has the advantage of being sulphur-free and of low ash content compared to other types of industrial lignin resulting in more pure lignin as a by-product [10]. In this framework, an OL-based reagent is developed for utilization in beneficiation process as a more environmentally friendly solution.

The scope of this study is to quantify the environmental impact of xanthates' use in the beneficiation process and evaluate the feasibility of partially replacing the xanthate reagent with organosolv lignin nanoparticles (OLN) reagent in the flotation process. The present work aims to compare the life cycle environmental impact of the established process of using only xanthates and the integration of OLN in the process. Life Cycle

corresponding author: peppas@metal.ntua.gr

Assessment (LCA) as a well-established tool for evaluating the environmental impact and sustainable development, was implemented to fulfil this objective. The gate-to-gate model that was developed, considers the base case scenario of using 100% xanthates as collector reagents and the alternative proposed scenario of using 50% xanthates and 50% OLN reagent as collectors in the flotation process. The schemes outlined are based on a case study applied in the framework of the *BATTERFLAI* project. The partial Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) was completed using the models. This study will serve for the quantification of the environmental impact of the two cases which will lead to their accurate and justified comparison.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

LCA Methodology

LCA is a standardized method for assessing the environmental aspects associated with a product, process or service over its life cycle measuring a list of impacts on local, regional and global levels [14]. To assess and compare the environmental impact of xanthates and OLN use in flotation process, an LCA was performed. The standardized procedures as described by ISO 14040:2006 and ISO 14044:2006, and the International Life Cycle Data (ILCD) Handbook [15-17]. The LCA is an interoperable process that consists of four stages: (i) Goal and Scope definition, (ii) Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), (iii) Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) and (iv) Interpretation of the results. The modelling of the different cases was performed with the commercial software Sphera LCA FE.

Goal, Scope and Functional Unit

In the framework of goal and scope definition the purpose of the assessment is established and decisions are made about the details of the studied product system including the selection of the functional unit (FU) [18]. The FU is a quantified description of the function of a product that serves as the reference basis for all calculations regarding impact assessment [19].

A gate-to-gate LCA was conducted to assess the environmental impact outcoming from the use of the xanthate reagent. The scope of the LCA was to investigate the environmental benefits of partially replacing xanthates with OLN reagent in flotation process. The FU selected was 1 kg of ore that will be processed.

Scenarios description and System boundaries

The analysis of the flotation process emphasises in the reagents used, to guarantee the comparison accuracy. Two different scenarios were developed. In the base case scenario (BCS) xanthate is used as the collector reagent in the flotation process. In the scenario 1 (S1) there is used 50% xanthate and 50% OLN reagent as collector. Into the system boundaries except for the flotation process where included the processes of reagents production as well.

Life Cycle Inventory

Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) involves the data compilation to quantify resource use (energy, water, chemicals use) and exiting products and emissions (product, wastes, emissions to soil, etc.) for each process defined in the system boundaries [20].

corresponding author: peppas@metal.ntua.gr

Life Cycle Impact Assessment

The LCIA quantifies the environmental impacts using the results of the LCI analysis and the impact factors. The mass of the environmental load is associated with the FU [20-22]. The impact categories selected, (i) Climate change, default, excl. biogenic carbon (kg CO₂ eq.), (ii) Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEP) (kg 1,4-Db eq.), (iii) Human toxicity, cancer (HTP) (kg 1,4-Db eq.), (iv) Photochemical Ozone Formation, Human Health (POFP) (kg NO_x eq.) and (v) Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEP) (kg 1,4-Db eq.), are in accordance with Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCR) Guidance, in line with the scope of the study and complying with ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards. As xanthates are considered toxic chemicals, the main focus is on the toxicological evaluation of its reaction and the impact on humans and environment. The evaluation method chosen for the impact assessment is ReCiPe 2016 (E) to be in line with literature review for comparison reasons.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

In this section are presented the outcomes resulting from the comparison of the two evaluated scenarios. In the first scenario, which is the base case scenario, the flotation process is realised using xanthate reagent as collector. In the second scenario the xanthate reagent is replaced by OLN reagent at the rate of 50%. In all impact categories evaluated, the S1 shows to decrease the environmental impact of the flotation process. The Climate Change have a decreased impact of 0.03%, while the toxicity related impact categories, FWP, HTP, POFP and TEP have a decrease of 39.88%, 0.07%, 0.24% and 0.04% respectively. **Table 1** summaries the results of BCS and the S1 for each category.

Table 1. LCIA results for 1 kg of ore treated within the flotation process

Impact Category	BCS	S1
Climate change, default, excl. biogenic carbon (kg CO ₂ eq.)	4.6630E-02	4.6615E-02
FEP (kg 1,4-Db eq.)	2.1817E-05	1.3116E-05
HTP (kg 1,4-Db eq.)	2.1754E-04	2.1738E-04
POFP (kg NO _x eq.)	6.5480E-05	6.5327E-05
TEP (kg 1,4-Db eq.)	1.7718E-02	1.7711E-02

Discussion

Xanthate reagents are a standardized reagent used in the mineral beneficiation process of sulphide ores. Its decomposition, and especially the release of CS₂ raises concerns regarding their impact in terms of safety, health, and environment. The replacement of a consolidated reagent as xanthates in the mining industry may be proven challenging.

Considering the huge amounts of minerals processed in the mining industry using xanthates, generates the necessity for the partially or entirely replacement of xanthates. Thus, the development of more environmentally friendly reagents that will enable the same efficiency and will be more sustainable is a solution.

corresponding author: peppas@metal.ntua.gr

The use of lignin-based reagents is a promising option. Lignin is a low-cost organic material that occurs from side streams or from forest residues and can be found in great amounts. Taking advantage of such materials, leads towards the path of a more environmentally friendly and sustainable economy.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study highlight the concerns raised regarding the impact of xanthates' use. Xanthates decomposition affects environment and human health. The reduction of xanthates use can improve significantly the environmental and safety performance of beneficiation process of the sulphide ores.

The LCA implemented and presented in this study, shows that there is an important improvement of flotation process impact by replacing the 50% of the xanthate reagent with an eco-friendlier reagent as is OLN. In all of the impact categories evaluated, the impact has been improved, with the greatest improvement of 39.88% to be observed in the case of FEP.

It is evident that the use of an alternative reagent, as OLN proposed in this study can efficiently replace xanthates, at the specific ratio analysed, resulting to important environmental improvement.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research has received funding from the EIT RawMaterials research and innovation programme under Proposal Number n°19089, project BATTERFLAI. Supply of BATTERY minerals using lignin nanoparticles as FLOTATION collectors.

REFERENCES

1. Min, Q., et al., *Froth Flotation of Mineral Particles: Mechanism*. Drying Technology, 2008. **26**(8): p. 985-995.
2. Wang, D. and Q. Liu, *Hydrodynamics of froth flotation and its effects on fine and ultrafine mineral particle flotation: A literature review*. Minerals Engineering, 2021. **173**: p. 107220.
3. Prudence Bararunyeretse, P.C.M., Lambert Niyoyitungiye, Simon Buhungu, *Essentiality, Fate, Ecotoxicity, and Health Effects of Xanthates and Xanthates Based-Compounds—A Review*. Journal of Geoscience and Environment Protection, 2022. **10**(12): p. 161-203.
4. *Xanthates*. Market Research.com, 2022.
5. *Xanthates Market is expected to expand at a CAGR of 7% from 2022 to 2029*
6. Milosavljević, M., et al., *New Eco-Friendly Xanthate-Based Flotation Agents*. Minerals, 2020. **10**: p. 350.
7. Mokgethwa, M., et al., *An Evaluation of Sodium Ethyl Xanthate for the Froth Flotation Upgrading of a Carbonatitic Copper Ore*. Journal of Physical Science, 2016. **27**: p. 13-21.
8. Shen, Y., *Chemical Fate Studies of Mining Reagents: Understanding the Decomposition Behavior under Various Conditions*. 2016.
9. Hrůzová, K., et al., *Organosolv lignin hydrophobic micro- and nanoparticles as a low-carbon footprint biodegradable flotation collector in mineral flotation*. Bioresource Technology, 2020. **306**: p. 123235.

corresponding author: peppas@metal.ntua.gr

10. Yadav, P., et al., *Environmental impact and cost assessment of a novel lignin production method*. Journal of Cleaner Production, 2021. **279**: p. 123515.
11. *Global Organosolv Lignins Market by Type, Pulping with acetic acid, By Application And By Region, Forecast From 2022 To 2030*. 2021; Available from: <https://dataintelo.com/report/organosolv-lignins-market/>.
12. *Global Organosolv Lignins Market by Type (Ethanol/water pulping (Alcell process), Pulping with acetic acid (CIMV process), Other), By Application (Ink, Varnishes, Paints, Others) And By Region (North America, Latin America, Europe, Asia Pacific and Middle East & Africa), Forecast From 2022 To 2030*. 2021; Available from: <https://dataintelo.com/report/organosolv-lignins-market/>.
13. Jarrell, T.M., et al., *Characterization of organosolv switchgrass lignin by using high performance liquid chromatography/high resolution tandem mass spectrometry using hydroxide-doped negative-ion mode electrospray ionization*. Green Chemistry, 2014. **16**(5): p. 2713-2727.
14. Muralikrishna, I.V. and V. Manickam, *Chapter Five - Life Cycle Assessment*, in *Environmental Management*, I.V. Muralikrishna and V. Manickam, Editors. 2017, Butterworth-Heinemann. p. 57-75.
15. *ISO 14044:2006 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines*. 2022.
16. *ISO 14040:2006 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework*. 2022.
17. *Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)*. European Platform on Life Cycle Assessment.
18. Curran, M.A., *Overview of Goal and Scope Definition in Life Cycle Assessment*, in *Goal and Scope Definition in Life Cycle Assessment*, M.A. Curran, Editor. 2017, Springer Netherlands: Dordrecht. p. 1-62.
19. Arzoumanidis, I., et al., *Functional Unit Definition Criteria in Life Cycle Assessment and Social Life Cycle Assessment: A Discussion*, in *Perspectives on Social LCA: Contributions from the 6th International Conference*, M. Traverso, L. Petti, and A. Zamagni, Editors. 2020, Springer International Publishing: Cham. p. 1-10.
20. Fraval, S., et al., *Life Cycle Assessment of Food Products*, in *Encyclopedia of Food Security and Sustainability*, P. Ferranti, E.M. Berry, and J.R. Anderson, Editors. 2019, Elsevier: Oxford. p. 488-496.
21. Accorsi, R., *Chapter 5 - A support-design procedure for sustainable food product-packaging systems*, in *Sustainable Food Supply Chains*, R. Accorsi and R. Manzini, Editors. 2019, Academic Press. p. 61-81.
22. Kikuchi, Y. and Y. Kanematsu, *Chapter 27 - Life cycle assessment*, in *Plant Factory (Second Edition)*, T. Kozai, G. Niu, and M. Takagaki, Editors. 2020, Academic Press. p. 383-395.

corresponding author: peppas@metal.ntua.gr